

Project Deliverable D-JRP17- WP 6.Del 2

Workpackage 6

Responsible Partner: APHA

Contributing partners: ANSES, FLI, ISZAM,
WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Author	ANSES (Luca Freddi)
Other contributors	APHA, ISZAM
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DELIVERABLE REPORT D-JRP17-WP6.DEL2: COLLABORATIVE TOOLKIT FOR EMERGING BRUCELLA SPECIES AND RELATED RESERVOIRS

Description of the task

The toolkit will aim to improve accessibility to credible and up-to-date information on emerging *Brucella* threats of public health significance in a 'one-stop' format that is quick and easy to use. The task will take all the necessary information generated by other IDEMBRU WPs and will make use of the deliverables produced during the project. The work package will be split in two main tasks:

A collaborative toolbox comprising documents, guidelines, tracking system including emerging *Brucella* and flowcharts on outbreak investigations that may be needed for emerging Brucellosis outbreak investigations will be developed to: i) describe the outbreak with a minimal dataset (case definition, spatiotemporal data, species etc.); ii) define harmonized investigation strategies for emerging *Brucella* and reservoirs; iii) characterise strains with an optimised and harmonised set of methods integrating classical phenotypic, genomic and proteomic approaches and assessment of behavior in virulence models.

The aim was to develop a collaborative toolbox comprising documents, guidelines, tracking system including emerging *Brucella* and flowcharts on outbreak investigations that may be needed for emerging Brucellosis outbreak investigations. Specific objectives have been:

- i) to describe the outbreak with a minimal dataset (case definition, spatiotemporal data, species etc.);
- ii) to define harmonized investigation strategies for emerging *Brucella* and reservoirs;
- iii) provide the tools and flowcharts necessary to properly characterise strains with an optimised and harmonised set of methods integrating classical phenotypic, genomic and proteomic approaches and assessment of behaviour in virulence models.

Given the recent emergence of *B. canis* infection in several EU Countries, and considering its zoonotic potential and the absence of diagnostic and management tools, the WP leaders and deputies decided to produce two complementary parts of the toolkit: one focusing on detection and characterisation of emerging *Brucella* species and/or reservoirs (the one already expected as project deliverable), and the second tailored specifically for *B. canis* identification and outbreak management.

The two operational toolboxes, each one tailored on the respective target *Brucella* clade, are composed of reference databases, harmonised protocols, guidance on interpretation, tracking systems, flowcharts on outbreak investigations. In both kits, the detection of the bacteria is emphasised with accurate descriptions of currently available detection methods (eg. RT-PCR, bacteriology), including new method such as MALDI-TOF, anti-bio resistance tests, growth on various new nutrient deprived media, motility or *in vitro* infection models- RNAseq and cytokine analyses. These new characterisation approaches include functional markers such as, virulence, resistance to antibiotics, and development of *in vitro* models. A regular SWOT analysis has been carried out by all WP contributors in order to better drive the toolbox assembling.

The resources of the different WPs have been integrated in the two final toolboxes to fulfil three major objectives:

- 1) the detection and investigation of the pathogens of interest from different sources, under various epidemiological contexts in terms of natural landscape, livestock demographics and wildlife in Europe;
- 2) the characterisation of emerging *Brucella* by identification of genomic and phenotypic variability via high throughput methods, such as NGS, molecular tests, proteomics, metabolomics;
- 3) the understanding of virulence and zoonotic potential through *in vitro* infection models.

The final toolkit will be available on the websites of the One Health EJP, ANSES and EFSA, both in integrative and interactive form.

Another component of the toolbox is the PADIweb project. The project built a fully automated information collection system, based on Google News and RSS alerts system for tracking and early warning system of targeted pathogens. According to the key words used, the system uses artificial intelligence to translate found news, and supervised learning approach to sort obtained in databases and present the news through maps and other information systems. Currently the PADIweb search engine is in testing phase for *B. canis*, while tracing of information for wildlife and environmental sources for non-core clade species needs additional refinements. The estimated time necessary to verify the system performances would be until the final toolkit submission. Furthermore, PADIweb data collection will be also available as an epidemiological tracking system for EU referent laboratory and EFSA.